

**Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe
Phase 3**

**Communication, Dissemination, and
Exploitation Plan (CDEP)
Deliverable D6.1**

EuroHPC
Joint Undertaking

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ESiWACE3 Deliverable D6.1

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1. Abstract /publishable summary

This document details the actions carried out and planned to be conducted, goals, target audiences, and tools to communicate and disseminate the project services/results and engage with the potential ESiWACE3 community. It is the “Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan” (CDEP).

The deliverable summarises the actions already performed and the mid-term planned activities for the first 18 months of the project—1 January 2023 - 30 June 2024—. This CDEP will be regularly updated with the periodic reports due in months 18, 36, and 48.

2. Conclusion & Results

The CDEP is described in section 4. It is the starting point for the implementation of the communication, dissemination, and engagement strategy of the project. It also lays the foundations for the potential exploitation of the services provided and results obtained as part of the project.

Updates of this plan are foreseen in the progress reports (months 18, 36, and 48).

3. Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to achieving some of the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Grant Agreement:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable?
O4. Support the wider community of weather and climate modelling in the use of state-of-the-art supercomputers via targeted services.	Yes
O5. Support the wider community of weather and climate modelling in the use of state-of-the-art supercomputers via training and capacity building.	Yes
O6. Build a well-connected and inclusive community for high-resolution Earth system modelling across Earth System science and HPC, and establish connections and knowledge transfer between existing European initiatives.	Yes

Specific goals in the work plan	Contribution of this deliverable?
Serve as a landing point for the European community of Earth System modellers to cooperate and exchange knowledge and expertise.	Yes
Strong focus on communication and networking activities to broaden the community.	Yes
Particularly addressing early career scientists and female researchers and contacting Inclusiveness Target Countries (ITCs).	Yes

4. Detailed report on the deliverable

4.1. Introduction

The Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan (CDEP) describes the strategy to be followed and the structures to be implemented to steer communication and engagement between the project, the potential stakeholders, and multiple audiences.

The CDEP represents the planned actions to be carried out for:

- Communicate the project and the actions conducted using specific communication tools beyond the project's community;
- Disseminate the results of the research conducted within the project to an identified targeted audience;
- Promote the project, its services, training, and results to the potential stakeholders/users;
- Seek interaction and engagement with selected audiences;
- Determine the potential exploitation cases of the research done within the project.

The CDEP also indicates the specific targeted audiences and which communication measures are planned to open a dialogue with these audiences.

4.2. Objectives

The objective of the CDEP is to set up the strategy to build a well-connected and inclusive community for high-resolution Earth System modelling across Earth System science and HPC and establish connections and knowledge transfer between existing European initiatives. Building a well-connected community is essential to ensure knowledge transfer and exchange across the many actors in Earth System science and high-performance computing, including domain scientists, technology providers, and end users.

The ESiWACE3 communication, dissemination, and engagement strategy aims to increase its outreach while achieving a more inclusive and diverse community. This includes creating a network of ITCs, by identifying and contacting relevant actors in these countries and sharing technical and communication expertise. The strategy will also promote gender equity by engaging in ongoing activities addressed to women in HPC and empowering female early career scientists (ECSs).

The coordination and support to the ESiWACE3 community will be based on three main concepts:

1. Sustaining and growing the network established in previous ESiWACE phases by providing new opportunities and means for fruitful interactions;
2. Anchoring the ESiWACE network to ongoing activities to connect the engaged community with other networks (European initiatives, CoEs, NCCs, ...);
3. Promoting training and capacity-building activities across the community.

The ultimate goal is to promote an active, inclusive, and sustained community, foster the uptake of the project outcomes, and maximise the long-term impact and sustainability of the project and its results.

4.3. Target audiences

The current and potential network of stakeholders and users interested in the project results has been mapped (Milestone M6.1). On the one hand, it aimed to identify which communication/engagement actions from previous ESiWACE phases could be improved to adequately determine the actions to be conducted in the current phase. And on the other hand, it also sought to get to know the community of potential users/stakeholders of the services offered as part of the project, as well as to address any gaps that may have been unravelled in the previous phases of the project. The goal was to identify those audiences to which ESiWACE did not arrive during previous phases, understand why and, eventually, try to engage with them.

Within this context, a series of interviews, surveys, and information collection by the consortium members were conducted (see more details in [subsection 4.4.2](#)), allowing the mapping of different kinds of stakeholders who could eventually be identified as different target audiences. See Figure 1.

Figure 1. Mapping of current and potential stakeholders.

According to this map, the main target groups for the communication and dissemination activities are identified below:

- Scientific community (Earth System modellers)
- HPC community
- Training participants
- HPC industry (HPC technologists, technology providers, high-capacity data experts...)
- EuroHPC/EC ecosystem (European digital agenda-related initiatives, CoEs, NCCs, ...)

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- Policy-makers

4.4. Planned actions

Communication, dissemination, engagement, and exploitation are crucial to maximise the project's scientific, economic, and societal impact. The purpose of the activities conducted within this framework is to enhance the visibility of the goals and outcomes of the project and increase awareness of how a new generation of weather and climate models that allow realistic simulations of the Earth System can improve our understanding of weather risks in a changing climate. All project partners contribute to these activities, monitored through target indicators, followed up and updated to maximise their impact.

Communication and dissemination activities and materials are crucial to support the ESiWACE3 project community engagement and to reach all relevant target audiences. Table 1 (from the Grant Agreement) lists the community engagement (CE), communication (C) and dissemination (D) activities planned in ESiWACE3.

Table 1. List of the community engagement (CE), communication (C), and dissemination (D) activities planned.

Table 4: List of community engagement (CE), communication (C) and dissemination (D) activities planned in ESiWACE3

Type	Activity (target group)	Description and purpose (target indicator)
C	Project website (all)	Maintain and update the existing ESiWACE website, the project's main communication hub, aimed at those involved or interested in the project. It provides the project description, latest news, events, reports, press releases, public deliverables, publications and all the communication materials (>400 visits)
C	Social media (all)	Regular posts will be made to reach a wider community, raise awareness and increase project visibility. We will build on ESiWACE social media accounts (Twitter and YouTube) (>700 followers on Twitter)
C	Communication kit (all)	Set of communication materials, including a brochure, presentation and poster templates, roll-up, and a presentation video (>250 video views)
C	Newsletters (all)	Quarterly project newsletters will be distributed to communicate about the project to the community of interest (people subscribed to the ESiWACE mailing list) (>350 subscribers reached)
C	Press releases (journalists, all)	Press/media releases and briefing materials aimed to generate interest in the project, communicate about events and disseminate results at a local and EU level (2 press releases)
C/D	Videos (all)	The project will produce different types of videos that will help communicate the project objectives, status, and results obtained to various audiences. These may include science explainers, project scientists' biographies, and videos documenting project events. Videos with a selection of the new services developed in WP4 will be created (>200 views/video)
CE	Clustering activities (scientific community, European Digital Agenda, EuroHPC ecosystem)	The project will cluster with other projects and initiatives relevant to HPC for Earth system modelling, such as Destination Earth, other EuroHPC funded COE's and related CSA activities, the ENES ¹⁰ network and national and international projects including NextGEMS, Warm World, ACROSS, MAELSTROM and EXCLAIM (>5 participated activities)
D	Scientific publications (scientific community)	Public project reports and publications in peer-reviewed journals will disseminate key project findings to academic audiences (>20 publications)

Type	Activity (target group)	Description and purpose (target indicator)
	EuroHPC ecosystem)	
CE	Organisation of ENES HPC conference (scientific community, EuroHPC ecosystem)	The organisation of two joint ENES HPC workshop editions (2024 and 2026) will allow a deeper engagement with the project's community of interest (>50 participants/conference)
CE	Activities to reach ITCs, women and ECSs (specific networks)	Individuals and institutions from ITCs will be engaged by sharing technical and communication expertise (>= 5 established contacts) Gender equity will be promoted in the events organised by the project (>20% female participation) Engagement with Early-Career Scientists (ECSs) will give particular attention in the events organised by the project (>40% ECS participation)
D	Slide decks and factsheets (scientific community, HPC technology providers)	Slide decks and factsheets to help disseminate the catalogue of new services created in ESiWACE3 or any other relevant project outcome (>4 services showcased)
CE	Hackathons (scientific community)	Four hackathons to provide hands-on training on ESiWACE3 developments, support the exploitation and sustainability of ESiWACE3 services, and enhance the collaboration within the European modelling community (>80 participants)
CE	Summer schools (ECSs)	Two summer schools targeted at early career scientists to train a new generation of weather and climate modellers to effectively use the latest HPC environments (>60 ECSs)
D	Training materials (scientific community, ECSs)	Teaching material to transfer knowledge on specific project-related topics that will be published online and advertised in relevant platforms to reach a wide audience (>50 downloads)

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4.4.1. Communication (Task 6.1)

The communication actions aim to reach the project target groups and increase the project visibility, demonstrating how the new generation of high-resolution Earth System models can contribute to tackling societal challenges linked to climate change.

Several communication tools and channels are used to inform all target audiences at a local, national, and EU level about the project goals and key messages and maximise the impact of the project communication. These tools and channels include (among others): a revision and update of the existing ESiWACE visual identity; the maintenance, revision, update, and curation of new content of the established [ESiWACE website](#); the social media channels ([Twitter](#), [LinkedIn](#), [YouTube](#), and [Vimeo](#)); new communication material (communication kit, videos, infographics, roll-up, etc.), press releases; and quarterly ESiWACE newsletters. Communication materials will be available on the project website and advertised on social media channels.

The forthcoming communication activities and their impact will be reported in regular updates of the CDEP (i.e. D6.2-6.4).

Table 2 shows the actions already done and planned regarding the communication of the project.

Table 2. Communication actions already done and planned for the coming months.

Activity	Actions done	Actions planned
Visual identity	Review of the visual identity (creation of a new logo and new colour palette)	-
Communication kit	Update templates according to the new visual identity	Creation of new material (leaflet, rollup, infographics, etc.) according to the project's evolution and necessities
Project website	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Review and update the website's static content to present the new phase of the project Creation of new dynamic content 	Creation of new dynamic content (news, events, job offers, ...) according to the project's evolution and necessities
Social media	Take over the social media channels already existing from previous phases (Twitter and YouTube)	Open new social media channels (LinkedIn and Vimeo)
Newsletter	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Take over the management of the newsletter. Creation of a new template for the newsletter. Release of the 1st issue of the newsletter (end of June/beginning of July) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Release of further quarterly issues

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Activity	Actions done	Actions planned
Visual identity	Review of the visual identity (creation of a new logo and new colour palette)	-
Communication kit	Update templates according to the new visual identity	Creation of new material (leaflet, rollup, infographics, etc.) according to the project's evolution and necessities
Videos	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website announcement of the "The ESiWACE3 week" social media campaign announcing the release of the new website content and the publication of 8 videos presenting the project. • Community mailing list announcement of the "The ESiWACE3 week" social media campaign. • "The ESiWACE3 week" social media campaign. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recall the videos campaign whenever appropriate • Further communication campaigns to promote the dissemination videos (ESiWACE2 services catalogue, ESiWACE3 services catalogue, Hackathons and summer schools, scientist's bios, ...)
Project partners' communication campaign	"#MeetESiWACE3Partners" campaign presenting the partners of the ESiWACE3 Consortium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recall the partners' campaign whenever appropriate
Press Releases	-	Required actions according to the achievement of some newsworthy results

4.4.2. Engagement (Tasks 6.2 & 6.3)

Building a well-connected community is essential to ensure knowledge transfer and exchange across the many actors in Earth System Science and HPC, including domain scientists, technology providers, and end users. The ESiWACE3 engagement strategy includes creating a network of [Inclusiveness Target Countries](#) (ITCs), promoting gender equity by engaging in ongoing activities addressed to women in HPC, attracting, retaining, and advancing more high-quality female scientific researchers and empowering female early career scientists (ECSS). The aim is to enhance the ESiWACE3 community engagement, mainly focusing on increasing its outreach while achieving a more active, inclusive, gender-balanced, diverse, and sustained community.

Clustering with other European projects and initiatives will also be fostered. These interactions will ensure links with the European ecosystem of HPC stakeholders and initiatives related to the European digital agenda. The objective is to raise awareness of the project topics and results of interest for the community. It includes the organisation of the joint ENES HPC Workshops editions for 2024 and 2026, the coordination of project requests of HPC resources through the EuroHPC CoE call, and the participation of ESiWACE3 in conferences/workshops/events (such as the EGU, PASC, ISC, etc.). The information on the participation of ESiWACE3 in conferences/workshops/events are collected in an Excel document accessible from the project's wiki.

In coordination with WP5, videos documenting the training events organised by the project (hackathons, summer schools, etc.) will also be developed and disseminated within the ITCs network. Gender balance and

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participation of female ECs will also be considered when promoting the project's events and accepting participants.

Upcoming engagement activities and their impact will be reported in the regular CDEP updates (i.e. D6.2-6.4), and the engagement strategy will be adjusted accordingly as the needs of the project evolve.

Table 3 shows the engagement actions already done or planned for the coming months.

Table 3. Engagement actions already done and planned for the coming months.

Activity	Actions done	Actions planned
Community mailing list	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Management of the community mailing list • Creation of a new template • Several communications already conducted 	Further communications according to the project's evolvement and necessities
Mapping of potential stakeholders (M6.1)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interviews with relevant people of ESiWACE, ESiWACE2 and ESiWACE3 • Surveys among the community (ESiWACE2 news mailing list, ESiWACE3 community mailing list, and social media channels) • Brainstorming among the ESiWACE3 Consortium 	Further analysis of the results obtained to identify potential users of the project's services/training events
Participation in conferences/workshops/events	Coordination of ESiWACE3 participation at events such as the EuroHPC Summit, the European Geosciences Union General Assembly (EGU), or ISC (among others)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organisation of an ESiWACE3 booth at EGU24, ISC24, and/or any other relevant event • Organisation of a Minisymposium with 4 talks on successful Services 1 cases to be presented at PASC24 • Further coordination of ESiWACE3 participation in relevant events related to its activities
Hackathons	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website announcement of the 1st ESiWACE3 Hackathon + eflows4HPC-ESiWACE3-Climateurope2 workshop • Community mailing list announcement of the 1st ESiWACE3 Hackathon + eflows4HPC-ESiWACE3-Climateurope2 workshop • Promotional campaign of the 1st ESiWACE3 Hackathon + eflows4HPC-ESiWACE3-Climateurope2 workshop 	Further ESiWACE3 Hackathons dissemination campaigns
Summer schools	-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ESiWACE3 Summer Schools dissemination campaigns. • The first ESiWACE3 Summer School is planned to be a shared event with WarmWorld project.

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Activity	Actions done	Actions planned
Clustering with other EuroHPC-funded CoEs, NCCs, and related CSA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Identification of potential EuroHPC-funded CoEs, NCCs, and related CSA to be contacted (eflows4HPC, CHEESE, BioExcel-3, MaX, HIDALGO2, CASTIEL2, ...) ● ESiWACE3 active in the NCC-CoE training materials task force established by CASTIEL2. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Organisation of a CoEs Open Day event together with other CoEs, addressed to high school students to raise their interest in HPC research careers. ● Identification of an HPC event to be attended with a unified booth and message among several CoEs promoting the use of simulations and supercomputing. In addition, promote the creation of content to be shared coordinately in social networks. ● Further identification of potential other EuroHPC-funded CoEs, NCCs, and related CSA to be contacted. ● Further organisation of joint events with other projects and initiatives (workshops, webinars, symposium, ...)
Clustering with other projects and initiatives relevant to HPC for Earth System Modelling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Identification of potential projects and initiatives to be contacted (such as ENES MTHPC-taskforce, Climateurope2, Destination Earth, NextGEMS, Warm World, ACROSS, EXCLAIM, ...) ● Organisation of the 1st ESiWACE3 Summer School in ● Organisation of a joint eflows4HPC-ESiWACE3-Climateurope2 workshop coinciding with the 1st ESiWACE3 Hackathon 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Within the framework of the HANAMI project, targeting a closer collaboration in the field of HPC between the EU and Japan, common activities between ESiWACE3 partners (in particular BSC, DKRZ, ECMWF), BioEXcel, and MaX also involving EuroHPC JU hosting sites, will be addressed. ● Contact the respective “communication officers” ● Exchange information on events and workshops ● Invite them to present at the 2024 ENES HPC workshop ● Further identification of potential projects and initiatives to be contacted
ENES HPC workshops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Calendar of the planned actions to organize the 2024 ENES HPC workshop: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Set up of the Program Committee (by the end of July 2023) ○ Set up of the agenda and identification of the invited speakers (by the end of October 2023) ○ Dissemination campaign (starting from November 2023) ○ Organisation of the workshop in May/June 2024 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Organisation of the ENES HPC workshop editions for 2024 and 2026 ● ENES HPC workshops dissemination campaigns
ITCs, women, and ECs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Mapping of potential stakeholders (M6.1) ● Identification and first contacts of relevant individuals and institutions in ITCs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Further identify and contact relevant individuals and institutions in ITCs ● Use the links with NCCs established through ESiWACE3’s membership of the NCC-CoE training task force coordinated by CASTIEL2 to make contact with modelling groups in the relevant countries. ● Promote activities to empower female EC scientists in the project ● Engage the project on ongoing activities of

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Activity	Actions done	Actions planned
		women in HPC <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Promote outreach activities to give social visibility to women in HPC
Requests for HPC resources	Coordination of project requests for HPC resources through the EuroHPC CoE call	Further coordination of project requests for HPC resources according to the EuroHPC calls
Interaction with HPC technology providers	Presentation of ESiWACE3 at the ISC23 conference in Hamburg	Identification of HPC technology providers of interest for the community and: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Plan specific sessions at the ENES-HPC workshops and invite HPC tech providers ● Invite HPC-tech providers to present at the ESiWACE summer schools ● Search contact with HPC-tech providers in particular at HPC related events ● Disseminate the HPCW benchmark

4.4.3. Dissemination (Task 6.4)

The primary purpose of dissemination activities is to deliver relevant and tailored information about the services and outcomes of the project to different target audiences using multiple editorial formats, as well as to promote the project results and their uptake by different communities.

An important part of the project dissemination strategy relies on video materials. First, videos have been produced to help present the project and communicate its objectives and goals. Another set of videos will include successful user stories to showcase the services developed in previous phases of ESiWACE. This will be followed by other videos with a selection of new services developed by WP4 to support the preparation of the project's new catalogue of services. Videos documenting project events (e.g. hackathons and summer schools) and project scientists' biographies are also planned. The video strategy will be accordingly adjusted as the project necessities evolve.

Moreover, slide decks will be developed to disseminate further the new services catalogue and other dissemination materials (such as leaflets and factsheets) showcasing the different services or any other relevant project outcome. The compilation of this material, together with the series of videos, will create a portfolio of the services created in ESiWACE3.

To facilitate dissemination, ESiWACE3 complies with the [Open Science policy](#) required by the "Horizon Europe" programme. This policy states mandatory open access to publications, and open science principles are applied throughout the programme. Within this framework, ESiWACE3 is committed to expanding and sustaining the [ESiWACE Zenodo Community](#) by adding new open-access publications created within the project. Scientific results will be published in peer-reviewed journals and presented at relevant scientific conferences/events.

All dissemination materials will be shared through the project communication channels. When relevant, they will be shared at project-related or project-relevant events. ESiWACE3 will also liaise with partner NCCs to make links to training materials available on their websites.

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The upcoming dissemination activities and their impact will be reported in regular updates of the CDEP (i.e. D6.2-6.4).

The dissemination actions carried out and to be carried out during the next months are listed in Table 4.

Table 4. Dissemination actions already done and planned for the coming period.

Activity	Actions done	Actions planned
Videos	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Identification of the services developed within ESiWACE2 to be showcased 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Videos to disseminate the portfolio of services developed within ESiWACE2 ● Videos to disseminate the portfolio of new services developed within ESiWACE3 (WP4) ● Videos documenting the Hackathons and Summer schools ● Videos presenting the bios of ESiWACE3 scientists
Zenodo community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Take over the management of the already existing ESiWACE Zenodo Community ● Update of the visual identity and content of the ESiWACE Zenodo Community according to the present phase of the project ● Review and update of the "Guideline for the use of Zenodo for the ESiWACE3 project" 	Expand and sustain the Zenodo Community through the addition of new open access publications created in ESiWACE3
Scientific publications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Publication of public project reports (Deliverables and Milestones) in the ESiWACE Zenodo Community ● Publication of dissemination material (presentations/posters/slides presented at conferences/workshops/events) in the ESiWACE Zenodo Community 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Further publication of public project reports (Deliverables and Milestones) in the ESiWACE Zenodo Community ● Further publication of dissemination material (presentations/posters/slides presented at conferences/workshops/events) in the ESiWACE Zenodo Community ● Publication of scientific articles in peer-reviewed journals to disseminate key project findings to academic audiences (whenever possible) ● Publication of scientific articles in the ESiWACE Zenodo Community
Services catalogue	-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Slide decks and fact sheets of the portfolio of new services created in ESiWACE3 or any other relevant project outcome
Software support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Website Announcement of the Call for Proposals (CfP, M4.1) for Services 1 ● Promotion on social media of the CfP (M4.1) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Further promotion of the CfP for Services 1 ● Promotion of the CfP for Services 2
Training events and materials	Publication in the ESiWACE website of the training events calendar (M5.1)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Publication of the training events material in the ESiWACE website and the ESiWACE Zenodo Community ● Publication of the training online material in the ESiWACE website and the ESiWACE Zenodo Community ● Online training material campaign

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4.4.4. Exploitation (Task 6.5)

The exploitation tasks to be conducted must ensure the knowledge management, protection, and exploitation of the results obtained within the project, which will be used in research activities beyond project partners, as well as for further development, creation, and marketing of products/services and processes. The variety of the above-outlined communication and dissemination actions will contribute to this exploitation of the outcomes, demonstrating the project's added value and positive impact.

The exploitation measures adopted include disseminating and transferring project results and open access to peer-reviewed publications and research datasets (see [subsection 4.4.3](#)). A particular focus will be dedicated to sustaining, continuing, and expanding the services developed as a prototype in ESiWACE2 to the community and its stakeholders and to identify potential products, their exploitation, and sustainability. We will define exploitation procedures and responsibilities within the Consortium so that all partners will be actively involved in the exploitation activities. All the work packages will foster the exploitation of results by the European HPC ecosystem and the HPC industry.

Moreover, we will also interact with the coordination of ENES Research Infrastructure (ENES-RI) that supports the Earth System modelling community in Europe, aiming to integrate mature ESiWACE services in their service portfolio.

Two exploitation workshops will be organised back-to-back with the project General Assemblies of the project. The first workshop will provide input to the initial exploitation plan, while the second will focus on the long-term strategy for exploitation and sustainability of the project Key Exploitable Results taking Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) into account.

Inputs from the exploitation workshops and best practices/experiences identified during the project lifetime will be consolidated in the Final Exploitation and Sustainability Plan (D6.5), which will also include planned measures for exploitation of the project results post-ESiWACE3 as well as for the sustainability of the services developed in ESiWACE3 and its previous phases, the co-created knowledge, and the established linkages and interactions within the community.

Table 5. Exploitation actions planned.

Activity	Actions done	Actions planned
Services	-	Identification of services developed in ESiWACE2, their exploitation and sustainability
Potential products	-	Identification of potential products, their exploitation and sustainability
ENES-RI	-	Establishment and functioning of coordination activities with ENES-RI
Exploitation workshops	-	Organisation of 2 exploitation workshops coinciding with the GAs

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Final Exploitation and Sustainability Plan	-	Development of the Final and Sustainability Plan (D6.5)
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4.5. Feedback

The statistics of engagement and impact of the communication and dissemination actions carried out through social networks are checked once a month. This evaluation will serve as a starting point for the update of the CDEP and will be reported halfway through the project (D6.2 due at month 18 and D6.3 due at month 36). A final evaluation and a plan for the project legacy will be provided at the end of the project (D6.4 and D6.5, both due at month 48).

5. References

- [Grant Agreement](#)
- [Horizon Europe](#)
- [Horizon Europe, open science](#)
- ESiWACE3 M6.1. (2023). *Mapping of potential stakeholders - Milestone M6.1*
- ESiWACE3 M4.1. (2023). *First call for projects in Service 1 - Milestone M4.1*
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8021025>
- ESiWACE3 M5.1. (2023). *Event calendar on training is online - Milestone M5.1*
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8086151>
- ESiWACE3 D7.1. (2023). *Project management guidelines - Deliverable D7.1*

6. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered

N/A

7. How does this deliverable contribute to the EuroHPC strategy

This deliverable is a preliminary plan to communicate and disseminate the project services, training events, and results, as well as to engage with the European Earth System modelling and HPC community. It includes several activities to be conducted to strengthen the links with other projects and initiatives, such as other EuroHPC-funded CoEs and related CSA activities, the ENES network, and national and international projects, including Destination Earth, NextGEMS, Warm World, ACROSS and EXCLAIM. See the description of engagement actions under [section 4.4.2](#).

Moreover, this deliverable is a complementary part of the "Collaboration Plan" (D7.5), in which the actions to cluster with the European HPC ecosystem are further described.

8. Sustainability

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All exploitation measures (see [section 4.4.4.](#)) will be designed with the sustainability of the services or products in mind.

Meanwhile, the following synergies have already been created:

- Synergies created with other WPs

A close cooperation has been established with the consortium partners involved in WP4, WP5, and WP7.

Workpackage	WP6 task	Actions done	Outcomes expected
WP4	Disseminate the old and new services catalogue	Identification of the services developed within ESiWACE2 to be showcased	Engagement with the Earth System modelling and HPC community interested in the ESiWACE3 services
WP5	Disseminate the ESiWACE3 training events and training material	Promotion of the 1st ESiWACE3 Hackathon to be held in October 2023	Synergies and engagement with the Earth System modelling and HPC community as a result of the training events (hackathons and summer schools)
WP7	Contribute to engage with the European HPC ecosystem	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• First contact to other EuroHPC-funded CoEs and related CSA activities• First contact to other European projects and initiatives• Show the availability to engage with the European HPC ecosystem and support their communication actions since we target the same communities	Synergies created with other CoEs (eflows4HPC, CHEESE, BioExcel, MaX, ...) and related CSA activities, other projects and initiatives (Climateurope2, Destination Earth, ...), ENES network, ...

- Synergies created with ESiWACE3 partners institutions

Most of the institutions in the ESiWACE3 partnership have already a communication or press office in place, which is in charge of releasing press communications through well-established channels and networks. Support from their side is crucial for successfully implementing our communication plan, especially for raising attention to upcoming events and the results and outcomes of ESiWACE.

9. Community engagement, dissemination, and exploitation

9.1. Target audience

As indicated in the Grant Agreement, the audience for this deliverable is:

X	The general public (PU).
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)

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	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This report is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

We are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience:

- Making this document available on the [project website](#)
- Making this document available on the [ESiWACE Zenodo Community](#) (the Open Access repository for scientific results)

9.2. Record of dissemination/engagement activities linked to this deliverable

Type of dissemination and engagement activities	Details	Date and location of the event	Type of audience	Zenodo Link	Estimated number of persons reached
Presentation	IS-ENES3	January 2023; virtual	EuroHPC/EC community	https://zenodo.org/record/8020509	50
Presentation	FDO Workshop	17/02/2023; virtual	Scientific community	https://zenodo.org/record/8036943	30-40
Presentation	EERIE KOM	24/02/2023; virtual	Scientific community	https://zenodo.org/record/8020499	40
Presentation	EuroHPC Summit	20-23/03/2023; Göteborg (Sweden)	EuroHPC/EC community	https://zenodo.org/record/8020521	100
Poster	EuroHPC Summit	20-23/03/2023; Göteborg (Sweden)	EuroHPC/EC community	https://zenodo.org/record/8020535	200
Presentation	CASTIEL2	18-19/04/2023; Virtual	EuroHPC/EC community	https://zenodo.org/record/8020572	50
Slide show	EGU	23-28/04/2023; Vienna (Austria) & Virtual	Scientific community	https://zenodo.org/record/8036985	400 - 600
Presentation	ISC23	21-25/05/2023; Hamburg (Germany)	HPC community; HPC industry	https://zenodo.org/record/8025411	400
Presentation	ISC23	21-25/05/2023; Hamburg (Germany)	HPC community; HPC industry	https://zenodo.org/record/8025420	20
Videos	ISC23	21-25/05/2023; Hamburg (Germany)	HPC community; HPC industry	N/A	400-500
Interviews	Community mapping	28/04-06/06/2023; virtual	Internal	N/A	N/A
Social media campaign	The ESiWACE3 week	21-25/07/2023; ESiWACE webpage, community mailing list and social media channels	All audiences	N/A	500-600
	#MeetESiWACE3Partners	19/05-04/07; social media channels	All audiences	N/A	500-600
	1st ESiWACE3 Hackathon +	15/06-31/07; ESiWACE webpage,	All audiences	N/A	500-600

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	eflows4HPC-ESiWACE 3-Climateurope2 workshop	community mailing list and social media channels			
Survey	Community mapping	29/05-20/06/2023; ESiWACE social media channels, community mailing lists (past and present phases), and Consortium	All audiences	N/A	500-600

9.3. Publications in preparation OR submitted

N/A

9.4. Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

N/A